

THIS DRAFT WAS PREPARED FOR A SPECIAL ISSUE THAT SUBSEQUENTLY WAS ABANDONED BY ITS EDITORS. IF YOU ARE INTERESTED IN PUBLISHING IT, PLEASE GET IN TOUCH. OTHERWISE, PLEASE CITE IT AS FOLLOWS:

Wciślik, P. (2023). *Jadwiga Staniszkis and the big tent of illiberalism*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12585321>

Piotr Wciślik
Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences
piotr.wcislik@ibl.waw.pl

Jadwiga Staniszkis and the big tent of illiberalism

Despite having discussed her life story in one book and two long interviews, the sociologist Jadwiga Staniszkis remains reticent towards biography as a genre: the sense of linear unfolding of one's life is an illusion, she proposes in a way reminiscent of Pierre Bourdieu,¹ what really exists are the turning points that retrospectively reconfigure the meaning of one's past. What does not fit into the new story fades into oblivion.² Mindful of her advice on writing biographies, this essay explores the possibility it might just as well apply to her relationship to political currents.

A shared trajectory?

When aiming to reconstruct Jadwiga Staniszkis' relation to illiberalism, one finds nothing that predestined her decades ago to end up in the orbit of that camp. Indeed, up until 1989, Staniszkis (or JS, as we will interchangeably refer to her)³ travels the same dissident path as the future leaders of the liberal public opinion. Every prosopography of the Polish dissidents-turned-liberals starts with the March 1968 experience.

¹ Pierre Bourdieu, "The Biographical Illusion" in *Biography in Theory: Key Texts with Commentaries*, edited by Wilhelm Hemecker and Edward Saunders, (Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2017), 210-216. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110516678-036>.

² Jadwiga Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe. Rozmawia Cezary Michalski* (Warszawa: Czerwone i Czarne, 2010), 267. Unless otherwise referenced, the factual details about Staniszkis' biography are taken from *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, or Jadwiga Staniszkis, *Ja. Próba rekonstrukcji* (Warszawa: Prószyński i spółka, 2008).

³ Another abbreviation concerns bibliography. A collected volume of her scholarly and press article was published as *Zwierze niepolityczne : zbiór artykułów naukowych, publicystycznych oraz felietonów z Lat 1970-2001*, ed. Piotr Chuchro and Jerzy Brzeziński (Komorów: Wydawnictwo Antyk Marcin Dybowski, 2003). When referencing that volume, I will use the abbreviation "ZWNP" while adding title and year of publication of the cited article.

As 1968 nears, she is senior colleague of Adam Michnik and his circle, which gathers around the legendary revisionists Jacek Kuroń and Karol Modzelewski. That circle will form the core of the democratic opposition in the 1970s and transform into leaders of liberal public opinion after 1989. She is brilliant teaching assistant in the Department of Sociology at the Warsaw University who might be sceptical about their revolutionary temperament, but nevertheless participates in their informal gatherings often to prep up the students for the so called “commando” interventions, that is, disruption of meetings with party intellectuals, asking uneasy questions and bringing up the taboo topics. She is against student radicalism, but when Adam Michnik and Henryk Szlajfer are removed from the university, she reluctantly participates in public protest, which is quickly met with violence of the security apparatus operatives disguised as workers. She joins the delegation of advanced PhD students to the University's Rector to present the demands of the student movement, most expedient being to stop the repression against the protesters. But it is too late.

What we know as the March 1968 events in Poland is a complex political and social crisis, whose stake is the process of destalinization started in 1956. It culminates in a series of protests against the government's turn to arrest destalinization, uniting students, workers and public intellectuals. The protests are met with repression, whose most barbaric face is the anti-Semitic campaign in the aftermath of which the community of Holocaust survivors in Poland is decimated by forced exile. Many of the March 1968 protesters are pushed to the margins of public life. For most of them this is where the story of the democratic opposition truly begins.⁴

For her participation in March 1968, JS is arrested, tried, and imprisoned for 10 months. One of the last to be released, she exits prison as an unemployed single mother (from before March). She is close with Aleksander Smolar, a fellow March convict, until he chooses exile in 1970 (to eventually become a tamizdat publisher and one of the most influential dissident spokespersons abroad). She eventually gets her PhD degree, finds a stable job, restores her reputation as one of the most talented young sociologists, and gets a prestigious scholarship in the USA.

Later on in mid-1980s, in response to one of her critics, this is how she connects the themes of her work to these fateful events:

⁴ Andrzej Friszke, *Anatomia buntu: Kuroń, Modzelewski i komandosi* (Kraków: Znak, 2010).

“Bieńkowski is correct in saying that a preoccupation with power and manipulation is characteristic of my book. Bieńkowski's criticism raises troubling questions not only about my analysis, but about my generation as well. Perhaps this is so because a core experience of this generation was the experience of being objects of manipulation (March 1968) on the one hand, and, on the other hand, of maturing to public life in a decade of repressive tolerance.”⁵

Let us start with repressive tolerance. As other lead figures of March 1968, she remembers 1970s as a slow emergence from a limbo of social exclusion and professional marginalization that was much harder to endure than the prison itself, and senses repulsion for the Gierek era of the unwritten social contract, promising personal embourgeoisement and Westernisation of the country in exchange for social peace. That repulsion is also something typical for the 1968 generation. Here is Michnik's image of the 1970s:

“It was a strange and rogue era. An era marked by upstart rush for enrichment, an explosion of material aspirations repressed for years, redeeming of which would come at the cost of moral conformism and depoliticization. Values eroded (...) The party offset salary raises with Western credits. The raises were however accompanied by - as many failed to notice - a campaign of systematic attrition against the leaders of the December [1970] strikes. Liberal passport policy enabled work abroad. Coca cola entered the market. Movies from the West appeared on TV and nightclubs offered strip-tease. Corruption was skyrocketing and censorship strangled step by step every instance of independent thought.”⁶

She identifies the source of that shared disgust as the policy of “repressive tolerance”⁷, one of key concepts of the Western New Left that informs her understanding of communism, as we shall see. In Gierek's Poland the principled stance of the March 1968 protesters seems ridiculously outdated.⁸ In that decade her bond with the fellow survivors of the March campaign is the strongest.

⁵ Staniszkis, *Poland's Self-Limiting Revolution*, ed. Jan Tomasz Gross (Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 1984), 312.

⁶ Adam Michnik, *Takie czasy...Rzecz o kompromisie* (London: Aneks, 1985), 9-10.

⁷ Herbert Marcuse's idea that what modern (capitalist) society calls tolerance is really an attitude of passivity in the face of misery and injustice, and of equidistance from reactionary and progressive forces, that works in the service of the status quo. The only possible driver of liberating tolerance can only be transformative ideas, even if their proponents are intolerant of beneficiaries of misery and injustice. See Robert Paul Wolff, Barrington Moore, and Herbert Marcuse, *A Critique of Pure Tolerance* (Boston: Beacon Press, 1965).

Once the structures of the democratic opposition are formed in the late 1970s, she participates in the informal lectures and seminars and writes for the samizdat journals. But it is her professional commitments, rather than the dissident activities that bring her into Solidarity. During summer 1980 she participates in a sociology of labour seminar in the Gdańsk shipyard, and strays into the shop floor to talk to workers. The impression she leaves is positive enough that once the August 1980 strikes begin, the striking workers invite her to join the likes of Tadeusz Mazowiecki and Bronisław Geremek as expert advisor to the future Solidarity leadership. After the Union is established in August 1980, she continues to support its leaders with her advice, while also being active in the open university movement bringing high quality education closer to the workers. After Solidarity is crushed and Martial Law imposed on Poland on 13 December 1981, she is neither interned nor goes into hiding, but carries on with informal seminars and critical scholarly work. She suffers health issues. Scholarship remains the centre of gravity of her life through the 1980s, in particular after the international breakthrough of her book *Poland's Self-Limited Revolution* (1984) edited for Princeton University Press by her fellow March survivor Jan Tomasz Gross, and *Ontology of Socialism* (1989) first published in the series of the prestigious dissident journal *Krytyka* edited by Adam Michnik.⁹ As one of the most internationally recognized Polish sociologists, she spends long periods of time in the USA.

On the surface, this is a life of a post-dissident liberal in the make. But in the hindsight, one can find some cracks in that image. The cracks that make her reluctance to take the liberal turn after 1989 more explicable, relate to the distinct way in which she processes the formational March 1968 experience.

For most of Staniszkis' young colleagues March 1968 comes as a moral and ideological shock that becomes the foundation of what would later be known as dissident anti-politics. The moral revulsion with both the state-sponsored violence and the acquiescent indifference of the society reverberated to pulverise the core of their political identity as young radicals: their capacity of heirs to the idealism of October 1956, a movement towards more humane socialism, and the myth of the revolution as the sublime end of left-wing politics would both be orphaned as a result. Against a totalitarian state that employed the dirtiest tricks of both communist and Nazi propaganda, and against the society that failed to oppose (and sometimes took advantage of) antisemitic, anti-intellectual and nationalist agenda of the ruling class, one

⁹ Staniszkis, *The Ontology of Socialism* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1992).

could no longer have faith in revolutionary radicalism, predicated as it were upon reformability of the state and popular support. One should instead take refuge in communities that allow for living in truth and dignity of the human person, and that together form a movement towards restoration of civil society, that alone can effectively force the system to reform itself.¹⁰

The emotional overtone of JS' experience of March is not only victimhood (which Staniszkis detests), but also frustration. Frustration with the failure to arrest irresponsibility of youthful adventurism before it took its toll on life and carriers of thousands of people mostly of Jewish origin. The derivative of that is the (personal) grudge against the young leaders of the March protest, since the consequences of their actions took away two men she grew close to in that period. Her friend Jakub Karpiński, whom she considers the biggest talent of Polish sociology sacrifices a promising scholarly career, fully internalizing the dissident principle shared by Michnik's circle that one should go all the way to demonstrate the firmness of one's convictions. In her eyes, Aleksander Smolar is reluctantly pushed out into exile by that same circle that wanted to have an outpost abroad.

Perhaps more importantly, the March experience leaves in JS a sense of frustration with not having seen it coming, with having underestimated the cunning of the system, the derivative of which is the cognitive imperative not to be tricked by the system ever again, and in particular not to be carried away by enthusiasm for the acts of dissent and resistance. That imperative shines through her academic and essayist oeuvre just like the flaring red lipstick defines her public image. She used that red lipstick for the first time at the age of seventeen to distract attention of her first great love, a ship mechanic, from a bad scar on her face she got in an accident. In her intellectual life, she would always be on the watch for the red lipstick, that distractor that turns the attention away from a scar-faced reality. Most of the time, hidden mechanisms of domination would be the scare, while acts of resistance and dissent would be the lipstick.

Critical theory and futility of dissent under socialism

Obviously biographical circumstance alone cannot account for adoption of given intellectual outlook. Another important factor is the type of critical sociology that was *en vogue* in the

¹⁰ Dariusz Gawin, *Wielki zwrot: ewolucja lewicy i odrodzenie idei społeczeństwa obywatelskiego 1956-76* (Kraków: Znak, 2013).

1970s. In Luc Boltanski's retrospective formulation,¹¹ this orientation aimed to provide both an instrument for describing domination and the instrument for emancipation from domination, but the way critical sociologists conceived the first aim made the second aim hard to achieve. The “critical” in critical theory is predicated upon the idea of reflexivity: the capacity of humans to incorporate knowledge about the society in order to change it, an arc leading from critique of domination, through indignation, to march towards emancipation. But the critical sociology of the 1970s (for Boltanski the ideal-typical case was Pierre Bourdieu, his former mentor) conceived of domination in a way that made reflexivity difficult to imagine. Domination that critical sociologists denounced was structural, enduring, total in scope, but also so pervasive that it was not lived or experienced as such by the social actors, who cherished different illusions of autonomy. Even though the ultimate aim of critical sociology was to guide social actors towards emancipation (and that assumes their capacity to step outside their subaltern condition), the identity of critical sociology as science was built precisely on the distance between doxa and episteme, the ordinary opinions, always partial and context-bound, and true knowledge accessible to the sociologist alone. And to protect its identity boundaries, critical sociology would often point out that the most powerful mechanism of domination is the illusion of agency itself.

It is not clear which came first: was JS drawn to this kind of sociology because of the scarlipstick dialectics that permeated her life experience, or did the interest in critical theory drove her to reinterpret her life story in that way? It is clear however that the way she tells her story harmonizes with the key concepts that organize her oeuvre before 1989, and these key concepts are either inspired or directly derived from the critical theory popular among contemporary New Left circles in the West.

Take, for starters, “regulation through crises”, a concept JS derives directly from Marxism, where a crisis is both an inflection point of the tensions inherent in the systemic logic of capitalism, and a moment of lapse of that logic, which allows for taking up extraordinary measures that reduce the tensions and allow for further reproduction of the system. According to Staniszkis crises of socialist economy play a similar “regulatory role”.¹²

Here the scar is the crisis resulting from the systemic contradictions of socialism. The contradictions in turn derive from the revolutionary ideology of the communist movement.

¹¹ Luc Boltanski, *On Critique: A Sociology of Emancipation* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2011).

¹² Staniszkis, “Systemowe uwarunkowania funkcjonowania przedsiębiorstwa przemysłowego w Polsce” (1980), ZWNP, 47.

Combining revolutionary legitimacy of the vanguard party that substitutes the Marxian proletariat as the agent endowed with exclusive historical agency and infallibility, the communists had pursued a fast leap towards the utopia of a rational society, they destroy exactly the thing that makes a society rational, namely the institutions which produce feedback loops and thus enable self-correction. That involved not only curtailment of political pluralism and free speech, but more importantly once the communists destroyed market mechanisms, gone were the measures of effectivity of investment that enabled rational planning. Bargaining between the centre and economic actors was a deficient substitute of these measures, setting the economic balance on the level of overinvestment, ultimately inducing crises.

JS defines a crisis of socialism as a moment of triumph of reality over utopia, “the moment of rejection of economic policy by the economy itself.”¹³ But crisis is also the moment to introduce the extraordinary measures that allow the regime to survive its contradictions, and that is the only mechanism of self-correction in a system in which feedback loops between the power and the society had been destroyed. Regulation through crises does not make the system more rational in the long run. Economic development in socialism can be only cyclical and unbalanced. If it lasts it is only because privileges tie people to the system (“in Poland one in every three males in the 30-40 age cohort is a manager of some sort” she likes to remind)¹⁴, and because the economic and the political moments of regulation through crises are usually separated (risky and unorthodox economic manoeuvres coincide with tightening the screw, whereas protest is used as a retroactive justification of changes that had already taken place), and that makes it hard to come together for different social actors pursuing social change.

Crisis, most of all is the lipstick. The spectacularity of a crisis, the hopes and emotions that observers and social actors alike invest the critical conjuncture, only distract them from recognizing its objective systemic function: the regulatory role. From that perspective, detotalization of socialism is a top-down, not a bottom-up process. The power itself uptakes the effort of self-limitation, because it understands that turning too powerful it becomes powerless.¹⁵ It achieves self-limitation through repressive tolerance and “lame pluralism”,¹⁶

¹³ Jadwiga Staniszkis, “On some contradictions of socialist society: The case of Poland”, *Soviet Studies* 31, no. 2, (1979): 173, DOI: 10.1080/09668137908411236.

¹⁴ Staniszkis, “Systemowe uwarunkowania”, 61.

¹⁵ Staniszkis, 60.

¹⁶ Staniszkis, *Poland's Self-Limiting Revolution*, Chapter IV, 150-88.

that is through creation of expert bodies and toleration of informal groups, whose function is to simulate the play of diverse interests, but without social forces actually behind them. It also compensates the deficiencies of socialist economy through a system of exceptions, that serve as shock absorbers while keeping the facade.

Notably, JS' argument is indirectly polemical with Michnik's new evolutionism, a contemporary concept eponymous with the strategy of democratic opposition in Poland.¹⁷ There detotalisation is understood as the effect of the pressure of the civil society on the system to reform. For Staniszkis, dissident reformism, radical as it might be, actually enables the system to survive. In fact, everything short of revolution amounts to complicity, and paradoxically the ethical rejection of revolution as means of political change is perhaps the only thing where Michnik and Staniszkis would agree. So no good choices for those who want to make a difference.

But then the revolution almost comes in August 1980. JS is about to submit for publication her monograph to Princeton University press. Ironically the first draft of the book that will eventually become *Poland's Self Limited Revolution* explains why something like Solidarity is impossible in a communist system (and the original title was probably *The Dialectic of Socialist Society*).¹⁸ She is able to halt the publishing process and resubmits after the Martial Law, in the knowledge that Solidarity was crushed and thus she was not entirely wrong.¹⁹

Her diagnosis, conveyed by the expression "self-limited revolution" will be hijacked by the liberals in 1989 to mean something positive: respect for the law, non-violence, compromise. She means it rather critically as a set of political and cognitive constraints which contribute to the failure of the movement.

The revolution could have happened. In the summer of 1980 there was a Leninist type of revolutionary situation,²⁰ she believed, in which the power have collapsed and society recognized a new centre of command in the Gdańsk Shipyard.²¹ But there was neither a Lenin or a vanguard party. Instead of political radicalism, Solidarity triggered an ethical awakening which JS considered a mixed blessing. On the one hand, moral fundamentalism helped the

¹⁷ Adam Michnik, "New Evolutionism" in *Letters from Prison and Other Essays* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1987), 135-148.

¹⁸ Jadwiga Staniszkis, "On some contradictions", 168.

¹⁹ Jadwiga Staniszkis, "Struktury nie marzą", interview by Barbara Łopieńska, *Res Publica* 163 (2002), <https://publica.pl/teksty/staniszkis-struktury-nie-marza-55351.html>

²⁰ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 147.

²¹ Staniszkis, "Rewolucji się nie robi, ona przychodzi sama" (1981), *ZWNP*, 115.

workers overcome their constrained linguistic competence in relations with power, a term Staniszkis borrowed from the sociolinguist Basil Bernstein to identify a political handicap workers had in a socialist system where, despite implosion of the communist utopia, the Marxist-Leninist talk still served the purpose of creating semantic hierarchies, driving a “meritocratic” wedge between those who mastered it (that included the ruling class, but also the intelligentsia) and those that did not. The workers considered these semantic hierarchies natural and inevitable, or reified, as Staniszkis would define it in Lukacsian terms. Moral fundamentalism of Solidarity had the double function of creating a collective identity around a sense of retrieved dignity, and of breaking through the barrier of the reified socialist “meritocracy.” It was thus a cultural revolution, which begot a fundamentalist mentality in place of political ideology.²²

That in turn made Solidarity profoundly anti-political.²³ The social movement prioritized witnessing moral regeneration over transforming the world around it. It preferred politics of symbols and status to politics of negotiation and interest, locking the Union in battles of secondary importance. Suppressing internal pluralism in the name of unity, it overemphasized anticommunism, missing the opportunity to forge an alliance with the anti-bureaucratic movement that was eroding the Polish United Workers’ Party (PUWP) and the state administration from within, but which collapsed in isolation.²⁴ Moral fundamentalism was an outcome of the “painful process of cramming that radical wave of protest and class war into a ‘trade-union’ formula”,²⁵ that dictated the anti-political stance and internal taboos on many political matters despite the fact that a 10-million strong social organization in a socialist regime was necessarily political. When the initial political moderation of the leaders was met with a wave of local radicalism and wild strikes, Solidarity turned to surrogate conflicts. It claimed the moral high ground and mandate of social oversight of political power, but refused to present alternative blueprints of reform. It wielded veto power to counter government action, but had no instrument to the sui generis general strike of the government, its inaction in delivering on its promises to the workers. It appeared as both embattled and intransigent.²⁶ According to JS, the revolution was thus limited not by a sense of risk-averse prudence (as

²² Staniszkis, *Poland’s Self-Limiting Revolution*, 115-35. More broadly, In JS’ view in a socialist society anxiety against ideological commitment prevailed, and in their function of orienting action, ideologies were substituted by mentalities - fundamentalist and pragmatic.

²³ *Ibidem*, 135-46.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, 82.

²⁵ *Ibidem*, 17.

²⁶ Staniszkis, “Solidarność wobec aktualnych zagrożeń” (1981), ZWNP, 86-106.

post-dissident liberals would later have it) but rather by moral fundamentalism that imposed cognitive constraints on political imagination. Although she was sceptical of revolutions in general, JS wished this particular revolution to go further.

Moral fundamentalism was just one “self-limitation” of the revolution. The other cognitive-political limitation Staniszkis identified was what she labelled as “inert structure” (*martwa struktura*).²⁷ The system was impossible to reform, because in the absence of private capital the interests of all social groups were connected to redistribution of state assets. Even the adversaries were complicit in keeping the system alive. The power elite avoided reform to avoid destabilization, while the trade union demands for change actually implied big state that would continue to be omniscient, if weaker vis a vis societal pressure. For this reason as well, Solidarity was a case of a non-transformative rebellion.²⁸

Obviously all that begs the question why Staniszkis debunks dissent as illusion, while remaining within its orbit. Staniszkis never addressed this contradiction directly, but she did resolve it. While she was often disagreeing with the dissidents on the theory, she had a convergent view on the practical reason of dissent which I would define as the reverse of moral hazard: one takes risks because bearing full costs of one's judgements is the ultimate validation of their worth. One's hands are not clean if one is just standing by.²⁹ Small "s" solidarity and critique are entangled: you owe the right to criticize a given group when you take risks together. JS felt that way for March 1968 student protesters³⁰ and Solidarity workers³¹ alike.

Between New Left and Neoliberalism

Critical theory *per se* is not necessarily illiberal, and it is certainly rarely associated with radical right wing ideologies. True, it can be a step in a conspiracist direction when the critic is not able to substantiate (including to other critics) her claim to superior insight into the mechanisms of power. A thought to which we will return. While this risk is inbuilt in the nature of critical theory with its two-tier social ontology (one social world for beginners, another one for advanced), it is worth emphasizing, restating what is implicitly contained in the argument thus far, that ahead of 1989 Staniszkis' work is virtually devoid of populist,

²⁷ On “inert structure” see also Staniszkis, “Forms of Reasoning as Ideology”, *Telos* 66 (1985): 67-80.

²⁸ Staniszkis, “W trzy lata po Sierpniu” (1983), *ZWNP*, 65-86.

²⁹ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 59.

³⁰ *Ibidem*, 88.

³¹ *Ibidem*, 141.

nationalist or conservative overtones. Instead, in a strange way it falls somewhere between New Left and Neoliberalism.

Her social network consists not only of the dissident circles of post-revisionist left, but also of the neo-revisionist circles around the “Colloquia Communia” journal, the Sigma Club at the Warsaw University, and the Otryt seminar in the Bieszczady mountains which she eagerly attends. She calls them “totalitarian utopians” but seriously discusses their ideas, as if that circle could have been a harbinger of party renewal (in fact they were quite marginal). At least as late as 1979 Staniszkis herself identifies as a “Marxist living in Eastern Europe”³² and —as she will later recall— in the Soviet policy circles her work is considered a “sanctuary of Marxism” (*kapliczka marksizma*) as late as 1990s.³³

Conceptually, her analytical language is replete with the New Left keywords such as “reification” and “repressive tolerance”. One of her main conceptual innovations, the concept of “regulation through crisis” is not only directly derived from Marx’s understanding of crisis, as we have seen, but also she uses that concept interchangeably with “artificial negativity”,³⁴ a trademark notion of the very influential sector of American New Left of the day, associated with Paul Piccone and the journal *Telos*, in which Staniszkis publishes throughout the 1980s as frequently in the left-of-centre samizdat journal *Krytyka*, edited by Michnik. “Artificial negativity” just like “regulation through crises” assumes that the system (in Piccone’s case monopoly capitalism) has the total homogenizing capacity that neutralizes all authentic opposition (“organic negativity”). In turn, that induces a “crisis of one-dimensionality”. Since the system can’t develop in other way than absorbing negativity (Piccone draws here on Hegel), it has to re-invent a sandbox version of it (“artificial negativity”). Piccone’s concept correlates with JS’ understanding of opposition as ultimately a sanctioned force of regeneration of the system, even if authentically experienced as a force of disruption, a “ritual drama” in still another variation on the theme.³⁵ A similar image that JS has of the opposition to communism in Poland, Piccone has of the iconic US social movements of the day, including the feminist and civil rights movements. In the most extreme version of the “artificial negativity” argument, Piccone observes: “while in Europe homogenization meant,

³² Staniszkis, “On some contradictions...”, 167.

³³ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 135.

³⁴ Staniszkis, *Poland’s Self-Limiting Revolution*, 279. For all her anticommunism, she gave credit to Poland’s communist leaders Gomułka, Gierk and Jaruzelski were taking risks to make the country more independent from Moscow. “That risk nobilitated them” – she granted. See *ibidem*, 200.

³⁵ Staniszkis, “October 1956 as a Ritual Drama: Case Study of Artificial Negativity” in *Poland’s Self-Limiting Revolution*, 278-282.

among other things, a brutal policy of anti-Semitism, in the U.S. its counterpart was the civil rights movement. Both aimed at eliminating specificity and otherness—one through extermination camps and the other through social integration”.³⁶

Finally, what situates JS on the left is a workerism of sorts, an attitude of loyalty towards the working class, the union rank and file whose trust she earned, combined with anti-establishment sentiment. By workerism I do not mean populism, since no populist would talk about non-transformative rebellion, inert structure etc. In fact, her landmark work, *Poland's Self-Limited Revolution*, was translated into Polish only in 2010, precisely because JS did not want to hurt the feelings of workers with what she had to say about them.³⁷ In fact, that book is not only a work of critique, but also a work of loyalty towards the workers and protest against the educated elite inside the Union who she condemned for disinheriting the workers of their victory. Working in place of ideology, the division between fundamentalists and pragmatists within the Union was a class division, JS thought, rooted in mentalities of workers and the intelligentsia middle class respectively.³⁸ Acting as Solidarity advisors, the educated elite wielded informal agenda setting power, for which the union leaders—not them—were later held responsible. In setting the agenda, e.g. demanding institutions of liberal democracy, the intelligentsia was driven by its own political imagination, rather than by the effort to understand how workers experienced the crisis of socialism, for whom these liberal demands seemed both abstract and impossible to achieve.³⁹

She preferred to work with the so called Network of Leading Enterprises (a Solidarity working group integrating activists and experts from the biggest industrial complexes in the country, which nota bene included Leszek Balcerowicz as well) on the strategy of active strike, in which workers would take over the management of the workplace.⁴⁰ She thought that was more true to the initial, anti-bureaucratic and egalitarian impulse which has animated the movement into existence, and which characterised the working class political culture more broadly. Anti-authoritarianism in general, and acceptance of certain liberal causes (such as abolition of censorship) was a product of that working class opposition culture, rather than an evidence of adoption of a liberal worldview.⁴¹

³⁶ Paul Piccone, “The Crisis of One-Dimensionality”, *Telos* 35 (1978): 48-9.

³⁷ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 185.

³⁸ Staniszkis, *Poland's Self-Limiting Revolution*, 24.

³⁹ Staniszkis, “W trzy lata po Sierpniu” (1983), *ZWNP*, 84.

⁴⁰ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 166.

⁴¹ Staniszkis, *Poland's Self-Limiting Revolution*, 51-53.

She observed how the public language of the Union gradually changed from the fundamentalist language of moral regeneration to the pragmatic language of compromise. Pragmatism was a smokescreen for the erosion of internal democracy, as the movement became less transparent, and more oligarchic in its operations, while internal dissent was marginalized as enemy of compromise. Gradually, the workers found hard to recognize their own voice in the voice of the Union leadership. The culmination of this process came with the Bydgoszcz crisis of March 1981, when Solidarity was on the brink of rolling out its nuclear option, the general strike, but ultimately withdrew. The Warsaw Agreement which ended the crisis not only was signed by negotiators behind the back of the elected leadership, but also couched in terms that made it unclear what the parties agreed upon. Reappearance of hierarchies built on semantic competence, she thought, translated into overall demobilization and resentment towards the educated elite.⁴² From that perspective, workers' acquiescence to the Martial Law was a failure of stewardship of the Union elite that alienated and demobilized the working class base. A failure that would inform her understanding of what happened in 1989.

To say that JS was loyal to the worker base of Solidarity, but not a populist, is an understatement, for there is an alternative path of her intellectual development, a path not taken, in which she would become neoliberal. In particular, her argument about inert structure and non-transformative rebellion of Solidarity is remarkably close to the kind of critique of Solidarity which is the signature position of the emergent neoliberal circles in the aftermath of the Martial Law. Whether you take the Kraków circle led by Mirosław Dzielski, or the Gdańsk circle led by Donald Tusk, or mavericks such as Andrzej Walicki, they all present a strikingly similar argument: that Solidarity was a form of “democratic totalitarianism”, because its political project assumed that the big state that would remain omniscient, if weaker against popular pressure, whereas Poland’s deliverance was rather in a strong, minimal state. In the neoliberal end game one should put economic liberalization ahead of political democracy.⁴³

Also, even though she does not use that term, her critique of real existing socialism has considerable resemblance to the neoliberal arguments against “constructivism”. In both cases capitalism (an economic order based on property rights, where market exchange is the main mechanism objectifying the value of labour) is the only really functioning and possible way of

⁴² Ibidem, 20.

⁴³ See Piotr Wciślik, “Homo Sovieticus and the Neoliberal Legacy of Polish Dissent”, *East European Politics and Societies*, accepted for publication and forthcoming in 2024.

organizing the economy and society, whereas socialism is basically a demonstration and a cautionary tale about what happens when one disobeys nature's iron laws in the name of an utopia. As she stresses planning in a socialist economy is "artefactual" since without the market mechanism, categories such as "profit" or "effectivity" cannot be objectively assessed. A crisis in the socialist economy is akin to organism getting rid of an alien body, "the moment of rejection of economic policy by the economy itself."⁴⁴ Perhaps it is not a nuisance, that in her aesthetic choices, she is a devotee of rebellious individualism. Her favourite literary figure is the Camusian rebel. We don't know what she thinks of Ayn Rand novels, but she does declare to have a soft spot for sturdy individuals struggling to shape their destiny against all odds that populate US fiction, which she contrasts with the cult of collective victimhood and failure that she considers typically Polish.⁴⁵

Manifold critique of 1989

If we are correct that in the ideological cartography of the dissident political scene Staniszkis should be situated somewhere in between the left and the neoliberals, the question of why she ends up in the orbit of the right wing illiberalism after 1989 becomes all the more intriguing. Paradoxically, we will not be dealing with a case of an abrupt metamorphosis. Intellectually, Staniszkis remains true to herself, and for that very reason diverges from the trajectory of post-dissident liberalism politically.

As 1989 unfolds, she emerges as the leading voice of critique of the transition in Poland. At first this critique first targets the transitional philosophy of political action of the liberal wing of Solidarity that comes to power under Mazowiecki's government, but ends up contesting the foundational character of 1989 as such.

Unlike in 1981, Staniszkis is not at the epicentre of the events. She spends the second half of 1980s recovering from cancer, and traveling frequently to the USA, on scholarships and to accompany her daughter enrolled in a PhD program in mathematics in Seattle. She returns to Poland in the summer of 1989, after the fateful June 4 elections. She is appalled by how, from one day to the next the Solidarity elite cut itself loose from any sense of moral obligation towards the workers on whose shoulders it climbed to the power positions.⁴⁶ Solidarity of 1980-1981, for all the "inert structure", was a genuine cultural revolution, an overcoming of

⁴⁴ Staniszkis, "On Some Contradictions", 173.

⁴⁵ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 62.

⁴⁶ Staniszkis, "Zachować Sztandary" (1993), interview with Teresa Wójcik, ZWNP, 119-123.

class divisions that promised a new standard of citizenship. In 1989 the Solidarity elite expected loyalty without voice, patience in shouldering the burdens of economic restructuring. That assessment will not change with time. “The ideals of Solidarity were realized only in half. We have not become an activist society taking care of the weak and in the process of permanent learning” – she will remark in 1998.⁴⁷

She does not like what Balcerowicz is doing. Notably, her reasons have little to do with worker welfare. She wants Polish capitalism to thrive. She just thinks shock therapy will not take Poland there. In her view, extinguishing hyperinflation by way of artificially induced recession (expensive loans, high taxes, wage freezes) has been destroying the little domestic capital which socialist middle class managed to accumulate, and which could have been invested in privatisation.⁴⁸ The existence of the private sector, not only the nomenklatura companies, but also the SMEs formed in the 1980s, was difficult enough without access to loans, and recession made it impossible. But it was also bad for big state enterprises which in many sectors of industry have taken loans to become modern and competitive, and now were struggling because of the skyrocketing interest rates. How Poland can have true capitalism without capitalists, big and small, she wondered.

The only group that was able to take on the shock therapy was the nomenklatura, which occupied strategic positions in the financial sector and international trade, and thus maintained financial fluidity in the times of money austerity. JS feared that could bring about “state capitalism a la Lenin” - an economic system in which the state regulates access of foreign capital to the market and keeps the domestic capital underdeveloped.⁴⁹ The Vaclav Klaus way of prioritizing fast privatization and making it universal in scope (through the coupons) was much more to her liking: while equally anti-inflationary, it directed Czech savings towards capital formation rather than banks, and counteracted the oligarchic deformation of the economy. In contrast, Balcerowicz set up the financial system in such ways that the banks, not the companies, were the fulcrum of accumulation of capital in Poland only to have the banks sold to foreign investors.⁵⁰

She is even more critical of the Mazowiecki government as a whole. She thinks that the post-dissident elites are characterised by deficit of democratic thinking, and that the political order

⁴⁷ Staniszkis, “18 lat minęło” (1998), ZWNP, 125.

⁴⁸ Staniszkis, “Sprzeczności okresu przejściowego” (1990), ZWNP, 366-68.

⁴⁹ Staniszkis, “Dwuznaczność” (1990), ZWNP, 192-3.

⁵⁰ Staniszkis, “Klasa Pasożytnicza” (2000), interview by Paweł Paliwoda, ZWNP, 469-73.

is drifting towards “exclusionary corporatism”, an oligarchic system in which two hegemonic parties (post-dissidents and post-communists), organized into highly disciplined electoral blocks, negotiate the key reforms behind the scenes, while offering a sham spectacle of polarization which does not serve to articulate genuine democratic choice. Such corporatism, whose model JS derived from scholarship on Latin America, is exclusionary in a double sense: it marginalizes smaller political parties and inhibits differentiation and articulation of societal interests, thus arresting the development of democratic pluralism.⁵¹

The tendency feeds on multiple factors. First, there was the precedent of Round Table negotiations, which worked precisely according to this model, at the same time offering mass spectacle of polarization, and behind-the-scenes negotiations in a small elite circles. Secondly, the Accords gave to the opposition leadership an extraordinary mandate, not foreseen in the law, and created the temptation to use law as instrument of politics. Thirdly it was the plebiscitary character of June 1989 elections, which were a success in pragmatic terms, but at the price of the non-articulation of particular interests of different social groups, in particular the workers, who carried the risks of political protest on their shoulders through the 1980s, and who were about to carry the burden of the economic changes too. Finally, that was a matter of political culture of the Polish intelligentsia to which the post-dissident leaders were attached.⁵² That social group historically positioned itself as spokespersons for the entire society, not unlike the communists who during the post-war take-over believed to be the avant-garde of the proletariat. Instead, democracy required professional politicians, who articulate diverse societal interests. Due to all these factors, the Mazowiecki government was not heading towards democracy, but rather towards “authoritarianism with authority”.⁵³

Mazowiecki used the credit of trust invested in his government to foster a plebiscitary model of politics, based on passive consent and barriers of interest articulation, expecting loyalty without voice from its own base and urging to delay political pluralization of the post-dissident camp. The plebiscitary model was predicated upon high levels of political polarization, and as the communist party unravelled, the post-dissident liberals evoked the danger of “non-constructive opposition” to maintain its high level, casting in that role the populist right who might be mobilizing the uncivil majority. “The new government consolidates convinced that the tactics of excluding those non-constructive circles of

⁵¹ Staniszkis, “Groźba Latynizacji, czyli dlaczego należy poprzeć rząd Mazowieckiego” (1989), ZWNP, 357-60.

⁵² Staniszkis, “Stan zawieszenia” (1990), ZWNP, 194-8.

⁵³ Staniszkis, “Autorytaryzm z autorytetem” (1990), ZWNP, 360-3.

opposition is fully justified. The society is not ready for democracy – this is what the new power opines in the back room. These short-term expediencies of stabilization and consolidation might in the long term imperil a real transformation towards a pluralist, truly open...political system”.⁵⁴ She fears that an alliance between post-dissident liberals and post-communists, in the name of stabilization, consolidation and “return to Europe” is nigh.⁵⁵ That alliance would deepen the impression of continuity with the old regime that the “lawful revolution” formula unavoidably created, bringing about an explosive combination of legitimacy vacuum and anger with economic hardship.⁵⁶

Whether instigated by supporters of Mazowiecki or not, that moment of polarization inside the post-dissident camp was actually of epochal importance. The war at the top, as it goes down in history, created the alternative axis of polarization around liberalism, an axis that with time substitute the post-communist divide. In the war at the top, JS supports the “acceleration camp” which emerged in the presidential campaign of Lech Wałęsa, and consisted of a variety of political parties, including the Center Alliance (Porozumienie Centrum, PC) of the Kaczyński brothers, and the Liberal Democratic Congress (Kongres Liberalno-Demokratyczny, KLD) of Donald Tusk, united in their opposition to Round Table power settlement. She thinks Wałęsa's charge against its former advisors serves to catalyse political pluralism⁵⁷ and that the acceleration camp promises a more modern form of politics, in which conflicts are clearly articulated, political professionals take over from dissident veterans, and intelligentsia vanguardism is curbed in favour of conscious creation of the middle class.⁵⁸

Notably, JS criticizes the Mazowiecki camp in the name of values cherished by the liberals, such as transparency, deliberation, pluralism (and capitalism undistorted by nomenklatura privilege), many of them feel betrayed. For them choosing Wałęsa over Mazowiecki, JS permanently chose her place on the political scene. As early as 1990, among the liberal public opinion, her notoriety as a conspiracy theorist would already be established,⁵⁹ despite the fact that she continued to be one of the most internationally recognized Polish social scientists.

⁵⁴ Staniszkis, “Sprzeczności okresu przejściowego”, 367.

⁵⁵ Staniszkis, “Przeczekać?” (1990), ZWNP, 199-200.

⁵⁶ Staniszkis, “Sprzeczności okresu przejściowego”, 366-68.

⁵⁷ Staniszkis, “Przed drugim etapem” (1990), ZWNP, 369-73.

⁵⁸ Staniszkis, “Stan zawieszenia”, 194-8.

⁵⁹ Staniszkis, “Partytura politycznych gier” (1990), interview by Janina Paradowska and Wiesław Władyka, 391-7.

In addition to the political choices, what contributed to that image among liberals was her contestation of the founding myth of the liberal consensus of the 1990s, the narrative of 1989 as a historical compromise and a lawful revolution, which served as legitimization for both of its heirs: the post-dissident liberals and the post-communists. Her own theory of what happened in 1989 was profoundly Tocquevillian,⁶⁰ a theory that evolved over the 1990s to culminate in her landmark *Postkomunizm*,⁶¹ but whose interpretative framework emerged in the early years of transition.⁶² It was the elite of the old regime that was the real (and until a point unwitting) agent of the breakthrough, while the dissident elite only participated in dramatizing the revolution after everything was already set on course.

More than the pressure from the Solidarity-led civil society forces, the fall of communism was an unintended effect of the reform-oriented activities of both the leadership of the Soviet Union and the local communist establishment. At the commanding heights of the empire it was a matter of strategy to create a buffer zone between East and West. It was a “military revolution”,⁶³ a political change triggered by growing military imbalance between the two blocks in terms of nuclear parity. Reacting to that imbalance, the military wing of the Soviet elite envisioned a pre-emptive strike on Western Europe from the territories of Central Europe, hoping the US would not respond to a conventional war with an atomic retaliation. The civil fraction of the globalists, aware of the possible Armageddon, pre-empted the pre-emptive military strike by negotiating a neutralization of Central Europe, more or less along the Austrian model: the West could expand its markets eastwards, but not its military outposts. The globalists were globalists not because they wanted the Soviet Union to rule the world, but because they devised strategies based on a realist understanding of the empire's position in the capitalist world system. And realistically –in JS’ reconstruction of their thinking– socialism as an attempt to avoid the fate of a periphery of the capitalist world order, was a double failure. It remained dependent on Western technologies and financial markets, without enjoying the advantages of economic rationality that was unique to capitalist economy.

The initial plan of the globalist was to let satellite states of Central Europe try out first whether being a dependent capitalist development would work better than a dependent

⁶⁰ Staniszkis, “Między Ameryką, Europą, a Rosją. Koniec polityki polskiej?” (1998), interview by Andrzej Nowak, ZWNP, 429-37.

⁶¹ Staniszkis, *Postkomunizm: próba opisu* (Gdańsk: Wydawnictwo słowo/obraz terytoria, 2005).

⁶² Jadwiga Staniszkis, *The Dynamics of the Breakthrough in Eastern Europe: The Polish Experience*, trans. Chester Adam Kisiel (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1991).

⁶³ Staniszkis, “Rewolucja militarna a koniec komunizmu” (1995), ZWNP, 133-48.

socialist one. Soviet Union would observe and rip the fruits via Comecon. In a distant future it could even follow their example, in a world-historically unprecedented move of an empire wilfully downgrading its status. Thus at the origins of 1989 was an failed attempt to keep the empire under control by redefining (in globalist-realist terms) its cardinal tenets: the role of the economic system in reproducing power, and relation with its dependencies.

If that plan quickly span out of control, it was because political capitalism was spreading like wildfire through the ranks of nomenklatura from mid-1980s onwards. Political capitalism is a separate branch of JS' theorising, and has four separate stages,⁶⁴ but in a nutshell it means that members of nomenklatura use the “rent of power” take advantage of public assets for personal embourgeoisement, and to occupy strategic positions in the financial system and the international trade. Not unlike in the historical transition from feudalism to capitalism –here JS remains in dialogue with both Marx and Tocqueville– that ascending class realizes that in order to continue to thrive in trade with Western partners, it must achieve exclusive and hereditary property rights to the assets it hitherto only exploited, and create a business environment characterized by the rule of law. In other words, that it must leave socialism behind, and hopefully in a controlled manner.

In Poland the Generation of 84—as JS would call the future leaders of the successor party⁶⁵— at first followed Andropov's plan of introducing capitalism without democracy, but run against the barrier of foreign loans, for which democracy was the price to pay. And so negotiations with the Solidarity establishment began. In this area, JS concedes, the Round Table format was a true innovation, which was subsequently copied by the communist establishment in other countries, including those there has been “more seats at the table than oppositionists”.⁶⁶ An innovation, but then again in the realm of protest absorption. The ritual drama of the epochal compromise was a smokescreen covering up the true balance of forces, the “revolution from top down”, and its lawful character only served to legitimize the privileged position of the nomenklatura in the new system.⁶⁷ It was the communists who were the active agents of history, ready to jump into capitalism head on (having secured a head start). Solidarity's self-limiting revolution might have been a catalyst, an impulse for the top-down decisions, but Solidarity elites were not its movers. Ignorant of internal dynamism of communism, and mentally still imprisoned in the inert structure of protest that reproduces the

⁶⁴ Staniszkis, “Kapitalizm polityczny i jego dynamika” (1997), ZWNP, 321-9.

⁶⁵ Staniszkis, “Oni się czają” (1992), ZWNP, 374-7.

⁶⁶ Staniszkis “Historia i przypadek” (1990), ZWNP, 189-91.

⁶⁷ Staniszkis, “Między Ameryką, Europą a Rosją”, 429-37.

system, they presented a much more timid program, offering the old platitudes of balancing the private, cooperative and state sectors, and inflationary policies such as wage indexation, that could only worsen Poland's economic collapse.⁶⁸

The particular points in JS' argument are debatable, but it is questionable whether they deserve the appellation of a conspiracy theory, or qualification of illiberal. How are they different from say Stephen Kotkin's arguments—influential in shaping the debate on the fall of communism globally—debunking the narrative of liberal revolution and triumph of civil society as a fantasy, while insisting that the real agent of change was the “uncivil society” of the communist establishment demoralised by access to capitalist loans and luxury goods?⁶⁹ Or his observation that Gorbachev and his men were as serious about rejuvenating socialism as about making this process safe for the world, averting the nuclear Armageddon?⁷⁰

Again, what contributed to the image of JS as a illiberal thinker, was not quite her ideas or convictions as such, but how they circulated in the public sphere. While the liberals would dismiss it as conspiratorial, the right would weaponize them. Dissidents turned right-wing politicians, who were either completely left out, or marginalised in the course of the transition, would eagerly bring her theses to their ultimate conclusions: that it was one big hoax orchestrated in the Magdalenka villa by two fractions of the left, the ex-Stalinists and the ex-revisionists, who colluded to perpetuate dictatorship under the false guise of transition to liberal democracy, by monopolizing all the key positions in the economy and in Solidarity political camp.

What made her particularly attractive to Jarosław Kaczyński, whom she befriended since the dissident years, was her theory about the role of secret services, which matched his own obsession with the “układ”, the communist deep state conspiracy. While she belittled the agency of organized minorities such as the dissidents in the collapse of the system, she credited the secret services with the key role of fabricating the ritual drama of 1989. Not only in Poland but in other socialist countries too, the transition would take a different turn, she argued, depending on whether it was a military or civil secret service ops, given the two branches had connections with different power elites in the Soviet Union.⁷¹ She also thought

⁶⁸ Staniszkis, “Okragły Stół po dziesięciu latach” (1999), ZWNP, 201-3.

⁶⁹ Stephen Kotkin and Jan Tomasz Gross, *Uncivil Society: 1989 and the Implosion of the Communist Establishment* (New York: Modern Library, 2009).

⁷⁰ Stephen Kotkin, *Armageddon Averted: The Soviet Collapse, 1970-2000* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001).

⁷¹ Staniszkis, “Rewolucja militarna”, 133-48.

that infighting between secret services was responsible for policy changes in the communist successor party, all of that without providing any evidence substantial enough to match such strong claims.⁷²

At the same time, Staniszkis, in contrast to Kaczyński, was anti-populist in the anti-Jacobin sense that ultimately she saw some positive sides to a controlled transition (as opposed to a bloody revolution or nuclear power implosion) and even to nomenklatura privatisation. After all, the ex-communist elite (and not the inert-structure captive Solidarity counter-elite) was the history-making class with interests vested in success of capitalism and the rule of law. Nomenklatura capitalism promised more rational use of state owned resources, and clearly divided property rights. Adding risk (ending the symbiosis with the state) the nomenklatura would start resembling capitalists.

From that anti-populist perspective, she is rather critical of the “acceleration camp” in action. While both liberals and their rivals framed transition as a struggle between authoritarianism and democracy, she saw two forms of authoritarianism - corporatist and populist, again not unlike the political cycles in Latin America. Corporatist state was authoritarian because it marginalised representative institutions, while leaving key decisions in the hands of powerful interest groups, both domestic and foreign, operating behind the democratic facade. The populist reaction was primitive in the sense that it reduced complex economic processes of capitalist transition to scapegoating the nomenklatura businesses, and the equally complex international power play to nationalist and xenophobic slogans. It confused the economic success of nomenklatura opportunism and totalitarian menace. The Kaczyński brothers represented “populism of the traditional middle class, not coping with the fast internationalisation of the economy”.⁷³ However, in her opinion populism would not devolve into full-fledged fascism, as liberals feared. Not only economic because autarchy was impossible, but also given the Catholic Church and the military were anti-populist. The president Lech Wałęsa knew that and that is why he abandoned the acceleration camp as soon as it brought him to power, to make peace with corporatism, enjoying support from the Church, the military and the West. In the end, as Poland entered the third year of transition, JS saw that the greatest casualty in the war between the two authoritarianisms was the shattering

⁷² Staniszkis, “Nie zmarnować narodu”, ZWNP, 459.

⁷³ Staniszkis, “Przeszłość jako przyszłość” 279.

of the myth about natural coexistence between capitalism and democracy, in which the latter was a greater casualty.⁷⁴

In a broader sense, the bond between JS and illiberal Right has been rather one-sided right from the start, not only because she was quick to be disappointed, but also given her intellectual legacy. Here the key question to ask is how the illiberal circles were coping with the fact that the critique of the transition they accepted as their own was authored by one of the most important neo-Marxists in Poland? Whose key contributions to analysis communism, the concepts of “inert structure” and “regulation through crises” etc were inspired by the discourse of the New Left, the dreaded neo-marxism!?

If one can hear history's laughter, this is in moments like this. In its drive to create counter-elites (and JS with her stellar international career was the crown jewel here) Right-wing pundits such as Cezary Michalski would recode her Hegelian neo-Marxism as a form of conservative realism of institutionalist variety. He would connect it to the legacy of historical Right, the *endecja*. This was part of a bigger project of whitewashing Roman Dmowski's political camp, whose legacy has been tainted by antisemitism and the fascist movement it begot in the interwar period.⁷⁵ What gave grounds to count Staniszkis among the neo-*endecja* realists was the overall style of her political thinking characterised by taking institutions seriously, by an aversion towards romantic gestures in politics, in particular the dissident ones, and scepticism about the workers as the progressive agent of history. It was also the fact that both her grandfather and her father (both named Witold) were high ranking members of the historical right and its fascist offspring, ONR-Falanga, respectively, and martyrs of the cause: the older died in Auschwitz in 1941, and the younger was a Stalinist prisoner. But to qualify her in that way meant not only to turn the blind eye on the neo-Marxist roots of her thought, but also on her own perception of that biographical layer as a burden, rather than point of pride. She thought that in many cases what passed as *endecja* realism was intellectual primitivism, and it was genealogical shame that pushed her to identify with victims of anti-Semitic campaign in 1968, despite their ideological differences.⁷⁶

The other issues that the Right needed to gloss over in silence included her position against the legal ban on abortion, even though she deplored her experience and kept distance from

⁷⁴ Ibidem, 272.

⁷⁵ Rafał Matyja, *Konserwatyzm po Komunizmie* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwa Akademickie i Profesjonalne, 2009), 34-5.

⁷⁶ Staniszkis, *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 22-23.

feminist identity politics driven by what she perceived as self-victimisation.⁷⁷ She would be even more vocal against the political influence of the Catholic church, assessing in 1992 that Poland was on its way to become a theocracy.⁷⁸ When in 2000 Jan Tomasz Gross⁷⁹ published *Neighbors*,⁸⁰ a book about an antisemitic pogrom perpetrated by Poles during the Nazi occupation which triggered a wave of historical reckoning, she went against the defensive impulse that prevailed on the Right, and recommended a humble accepting of responsibility, a position influenced not only by her biographical burden, but also by her second marriage to a son of Holocaust survivors.⁸¹ During EU Commission-supported protests against building a highway through the protected natural area of the Rospuda Valley, in which the PiS took position, defending Poland's extractivist mandate to belated modernization, she took the side of the protesters.⁸²

The godmother of inclusive corporatism

The apex of influence JS exerts on the right side of the political spectrum comes when she helps incubating the Solidarity Electoral Action (Akcja Wyborcza "Solidarność", AWS) in 1996. This is the last year of the first post-communist turn in power (1993-97). During a meeting organized by the Warsaw region branch of Solidarity, she calls upon the trade unionists to consolidate the right-wing of the political scene, an alliance which subsequently wins the 1997 parliamentary elections.⁸³

As its godmother, she envisions for AWS a program of "inclusive corporativism" and "capitalism for everybody" (in contrast to the exclusive corporatism and oligarchic capitalism) which has been her normative vision of the endpoint of the transition already in 1989.⁸⁴ While exclusionary corporativism of the elites, as we have seen, required a weak state and weak society, inclusionary corporativism was correlative with a strong state and strong society.⁸⁵ By strong state JS does not mean neither authoritarian or a "big" state, but rather one that is firm in commitment to the rule of law (eliminating loopholes on which elite

⁷⁷ Ibidem, 245-6.

⁷⁸ Staniszkis, "Ciągłość i zmiana" (1992), ZWNP, 149-68.

⁷⁹ Gross, with whom she conspired in 1968, exiled in the US, would edit *Poland's Self-Limiting Revolution*, thus contributing to Staniszkis' international breakthrough.

⁸⁰ Jan Tomasz Gross, *Neighbors: The Destruction of the Jewish Community in Jedwabne, Poland* (Princeton ; Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2001).

⁸¹ Staniszkis, "Spiralą w dół" (2001), ZWNP, 474-81.

⁸² Staniszkis, "Rząd w lustrze Rospudy", *Dziennik.pl*, 12 października 2007.

<https://wiadomosci.dziennik.pl/opinie/artykuly/201977.rzad-w-lustrze-rospudy.html>

⁸³ Staniszkis, "Odbudować Szansę dla Polski" (1996), ZWNP, 443-7.

⁸⁴ Staniszkis, "Groźba latynizacji", 357-9.

⁸⁵ Staniszkis, "Wszechwładza oligarchii – czyli co nas czeka" (1996), ZWNP, 293-9.

exploitation thrives) and robust with efficiency that comes with self-limitation. If not a minimal state, it is a state that prudently chooses its areas of intervention and non-intervention. Again, a “strong society” is not the masses that are spurred into action by a charismatic strongman, but a society that is strong with institutional channels that serve to negotiate the fundamental class compromises, organized into corporations such as the trade unions, employers' organizations, industrial chambers, banks, but also churches etc. A regime she believes actually exists in Austria and Japan. Inclusive corporatism assumed not only a compromise between the domestic capital (mostly SMEs) and labour, but also their common front in the fight against economic oligarchies of nomenklatura origin, that use political corruption to monopolize access to institutions that guarantee lower transaction costs and business risk. Thus, she admonished, AWS should fight for equality of opportunity for the SMEs that hire the majority of Poland's labour - in that sense the fight for capitalism for everyone was also the trade union's fight.⁸⁶

The AWS government, in alliance with the post-dissident liberal party Freedom Union (Unia Wolności, UW) enacts a rather vigorous program of four big reforms in the area of pensions, healthcare, education and administrative structure of the state. As soon as 1999 JS becomes disillusioned with their direction too. To her dismay the reforms did not arrest the development of political capitalism in Poland, but actually nourished its final reincarnation, the “capitalism of the public sector”, benefiting from the money flows released into the market by the state that met an increasing number of its responsibilities by subsidizing commercial services. In that regard, AWS reforms of the pension system and the healthcare system constituted the single biggest injection of public money into the market and away from public scrutiny. In particular government did not have any leverage over the individual pension scheme operators, who charged management fees regardless of performance, and that performance was poor because of constraints on investment. That benefited the oligarchy and foreign capital leaving behind the SMEs, whose class alliance with the workers JS postulated.⁸⁷ The other way in which exclusionary corporatism has been hollowing out democracy was through “cartelization” or constitution of bi-polar political blocks, which disconnected political conflict from its purpose of interest representation. Cartelization was already a trend in the first years of transition, but progressed under AWS, serving reproduction of the political class, and of the political system characterized by politics without

⁸⁶ Staniszkis, “Własną drogą do Europy” (1997), ZWNP, 419-25.

⁸⁷ Staniszkis, “Klasa pasożytnicza” (2000), 469-73.

power and power without politics (representative bodies deliberate on secondary issues, while strategic decisions are made without public debate).⁸⁸ By 2000 she concludes that a serious Right does not exist in Poland: “Instead the Right on the one hand, has broken the state, and on the other allowed political capitalism to morph into capitalism of the public sector, participating in this formula which is corrupt and economically inefficient.”⁸⁹

She is not only disillusioned with AWS, but also frustrated with the failed investment of her public authority, which further bonded her to the Right, and further alienated from the liberals, whom she suspected to be behind the rejection of her books by both Polish and international publishing houses.⁹⁰ In 2003 a volume of her collected scientific and press articles from 1970-2001 appears in the Antyk publishing house, with conservative profile and samizdat pedigree, known for peddling anti-EU and antisemitic propaganda. The contents of that over 650-pages reader testify to the substantial degree of her dislocation to the Right as a public figure after 1989. She is virtually absent from the liberal media such as *Gazeta Wyborcza* or *Polityka*, but regularly contributes to the rival titles such as *Tygodnik Solidarność*, *Arcana*, *Gazeta Finansowa*, or *Życie*, all positioning themselves as a counterpoint to the liberal media hegemony. With the new millennium, her media popularity will pick up again. In 2009 Poland’s top journalists will rank her as the best political commentator.⁹¹

Resisting globalization

After the disappointment with AWS Staniszkis abandons the hope for inclusive corporativism (the theme disappears from her writings), and focuses more on Poland's place in the world. Round that time, the title of her column in *Tygodnik Solidarność* is “Prophecies of Cassandra” after the Trojan princess who, cursed by the god Apollo, saw the future but was not listened to. The reason why her prophecies fall on the fallow ground is less metaphysical, but no less overwhelming: the entropy of governability in the peripheries of the global order.

In her telling, globalization is a force “that rips countries out of their specific 'historical time' (type and stage of development) and imposes on them institutions and procedures which are rational for a different stage and scale”.⁹² The peripheries are most vulnerable to the

⁸⁸ Staniszkis, “Nie mam dobrego słowa” (1999), ZWNP, 333-8.

⁸⁹ Staniszkis, “Klasa pasożytnicza”, 469.

⁹⁰ Staniszkis, “Syndrom czterech zmiennych” (2000), ZWNP, 343; *Życie umysłowe i uczuciowe*, 250.

⁹¹ Staniszkis, “Lubię występować w telewizji”, *Dziennik.pl*, 4 May 2009.

<https://wiadomosci.dziennik.pl/opinie/artykuly/148302,staniszkis-lubie-wystepowac-w-telewizji.html>

⁹² Staniszkis, *Władza Globalizacji*, (Warszawa: Scholar, 2003), 8.

“structural violence” of globalization, whose most disruptive effect is entropy of governability. Globalization transforms the hierarchical structure of the modern state, whose governability (in the classical, Weberian rendering) was predicated upon bureaucratic rationality, into a network that consists of interconnected clusters of institutions and procedures, each with a logic, or rationality of its own. In a network state, governability is the capacity of harmonization of these different clusters. In case of the post-communist state such harmonization is made difficult precisely because not all of the clusters belong to the same historical time, the problem JS identifies as “asymmetry of rationalities.”⁹³ Poland and other post-communist states aspired to accomplish a capitalist revolution, which meant completing the stage of primitive accumulation of capital, and occupying a position of producer in the global economic order, a sustainable economy that is not dependent on a simple sell-out of state assets, loans or subsidies for its reproduction. However, premature deindustrialization and liberalization of the financial system, as well as commercialisation of welfare services pulled the country in the opposite direction, favoured by the West, that was interested in expanding to new markets.

Poland became a market for the West, rather than a Western market economy. It lost capacity to govern its financial institutions (to foreign capital) and public funds (to “capitalism of the public sector”). Poland's capitalist revolution degenerated into a Burnhamite managerial revolution, where elites depend on the capital flows generated by the state (and the EU) for achieving a high material status, but are not capable of autonomous reproduction outside that parasitic relationship. The space of manoeuvre was further constrained by requirements of integration with the EU and further liberalization pressures of the OECD, each pulling in a different direction. “The weakness of the post-communist state resides fundamentally in its disintegration into webs each with rationality of its own, some of which are beyond the scope of control and coordination of the political centre of command”⁹⁴ – she would conclude already in 2001.

The strings of that web are pulled by the USA, Europe and Russia.⁹⁵ While in the early 1990s, Staniszkis agreed with the Soviet globalists that switching from socialist to capitalist

⁹³ “Asymmetry of rationalities” could be also understood in Ernst Bloch's terms as the synchronicity of the non-synchronous, in an interesting dialogue with Frederic Jameson, who identified "late capitalism" with disappearance of the non-simultaneity. Ernst Bloch, “Nonsynchronism and the Obligation to Its Dialectics”, trans. Mark Ritter, *New German Critique*, no. 11 (1977): 22–38, <https://doi.org/10.2307/487802>; Frederic Jameson, *Postmodernism or The Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism* (London: Verso, 1996).

⁹⁴ Staniszkis, *Postkomunizm*, 11.

⁹⁵ Staniszkis, “Między Ameryką, Europą a Rosją”, 429-37.

dependent development had clear benefits,⁹⁶ with time the sense of weakness and drift would prevail in her perception of Poland's geopolitical position in the new political and economic world order. Poland sovereignty was in danger both by the US policy of creating a buffer zone between Russia and Europe (later Jarosław Kaczyński would speak of Poland under Tusk's rule as the German-Russian "condominium"⁹⁷). She opined that the Bush (senior) administration subverted Poland's integration with Europe. She spoke more favourably of Madeleine Albright's policies under Bill Clinton.⁹⁸

She further suspected that the European Union wanted to partition Poland using the tool of euroregions, trans-national cooperation structures that allowed for deeper integration of borderland regions, leading to uneven development threatening Poland's territorial integrity in the future.⁹⁹ The part of Poland lagging behind European integration would find itself in the orbit of Moscow, and that divide would self-perpetuate with time, given that the economies in the West and in the East had different standards of transparency, ownership and procedures.¹⁰⁰ Thus the buffer-zone threat and the euro-regionalisation threat were not mutually self-exclusive. Her image of the EU would get milder once Poland joined in 2004, and in particular after adoption of the Lisbon Treaty in 2007, which she believed made the European field more even for the smaller players, even if reassertion of the hierarchies of state power remained a possibility.¹⁰¹

In economic terms, there was further tension between integration with the EU, and alternative project of integration with the global market, proposed by USA through OECD and NAFTA.¹⁰² The latter would mean extreme liberalization and necessity to suspend the national jurisdiction of the economy in favour of the international arbitration courts (where companies could sue states for any regulations that obstruct their profits). In particular, the still-born Multilateral Agreement on Investment (MAI) raised her eyebrows.¹⁰³ EU integration was more humane, but it was not clear whether EU civilizational standards would withhold the global competition. Importantly, the problem for Staniszkis was not that these global

⁹⁶ Staniszkis, "Fragment większej całości" (1989), ZWNP, 184-8.

⁹⁷ He used this notion for the first time in an interview in *Gazeta Polska* on 7 September 2010.

⁹⁸ Staniszkis, "Gdzie Rzym, Gdzie Krym, Gdzie Polska" (1992), interview by Teresa Bochwic, ZWNP, 381-5.

⁹⁹ Staniszkis, "Na Śląsku leży klucz do dalszych losów Polski" (1993), interview by Ewelina Puczek, ZWNP, 389-90.

¹⁰⁰ Staniszkis, "Chemia suwerenności" (1994), interview by Zdzisław Bielecki, ZWNP, 397-401.

¹⁰¹ Staniszkis, "The Two Parallel Contexts of Power: The Lisbon Treaty and the Global Crisis (new challenges for governability)", *Polish Sociological Review*, No. 170 (2010), pp. 147-170.

¹⁰² Staniszkis, "Między Ameryką, Europą a Rosją", 429-37.

¹⁰³ Staniszkis, "Przepowiednie Kasandry" (1998), ZWNP, 575. The MAI negotiated in secret in 1995-8, but dropped after France withdrew under pressure from a global campaign against the agreement.

pressures existed, but that key strategic decisions in that regard were taken outside politics, they were absent from public debate and the agenda of democratic representatives. She would conclude: “Solidarity won against communism, but lost miserably against post-communism. Post-communism in Poland means an amalgam of deformed economy and weak state, whose ability to concentrate energy (or the will to fight for a dignified position in the world and capacity to steer in that direction) is so low that we have become a resource which others model without much effort and on the go”.¹⁰⁴

Things seen this way, there can be only two types of politicians: those who simply yield to the global drift and the entropy of governmentality, and those who stand up and resist. Not surprisingly, according to JS, post-dissident liberals and post-communists belonged in the first camp. Post-dissident liberals were too naively pro-Western and too complacent to even realize the drift, and the post-communists, while not lacking in will or ambition to carry their political elite status into a head start in the capitalist economy simply failed to make position sustainable against the forces of globalisation.

Perhaps more surprisingly when two new parties emerge to consolidate the post-Solidarity camp after the implosion of AWS and UW, namely Donald Tusk's Civic Platform (Platforma Obywatelska, PO) and Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość, PiS) of the Kaczyński brothers, she first supports Tusk, in a moment of brief and intense infatuation. In Tusk she invests the hopes for generational change inside that camp¹⁰⁵, and she also speaks favorably of PO as the party of conservative ease, whose leaders, self-ironic, pathos-averse, non-ideological, connect with their constituency as "role models", in contrast to the pretentious post-dissident authorities.¹⁰⁶ She even proposes that PO enters alliance with the post-communists, under the nebulous banner of “neoliberalism plus institutions”. She is willing to put up with the ideological cynicism that would bind this alliance - after all ideologies do not make a difference against globalization.¹⁰⁷ The failure to even contemplate that alliance on the part of the interested parties, only confirmed Staniszkis' conviction about the risk-averse, lukewarm and thus non-political attitude of that liberal successor party,¹⁰⁸ even before the other failed alliance - the one with PiS expected after 2005 elections.

¹⁰⁴ Staniszkis, “Przegrana Solidarności” (2003), ZWNP, 126.

¹⁰⁵ Staniszkis, “Klasa pasożytnicza”, 471.

¹⁰⁶ Staniszkis, “Moda na Centrum” (2001), ZWNP, 558.

¹⁰⁷ Staniszkis, “Przymusowa liberalizacja (2001), ZWNP, 481-3.

¹⁰⁸ Staniszkis, “Wierzyć w siebie” (2001), ZWNP, 614-5

Does she think that the illiberal right belongs in the camp of the resisters? According to JS' own standards, to resist that drift required both a political and a cognitive capacity. To design better institutions and procedures that harmonize the tensions resulting from the "asymmetry of rationalities", one needed first to understand the global condition of the post-communist peripheries. Populism, by her own definition (forged when describing Andrzej Lepper) was a political language that "interpreted the dilemmas of modernity using traditional notions" which made it "emotionally appealing, but politically irrelevant, since it is not able to articulate problems in a way that is conducive to their solution".¹⁰⁹ In terms of that definition, the illiberal camp that emerged from the ruins of AWS, had a rather populist and traditionalist agenda, even if it paid lip-service to her theories of post-communism (at the point when she already announced its historical defeat). Not only culturally, in the sense of waging culture wars internally and pronouncing moral isolationism from the West, but also politically, in the sense that its political strategy was quite old-fashioned in its Jacobin way of state-capture, in the assumption that state is still the sole locus of power, the good old bureaucratic machine whose proper functioning depended only on having moral men at the helm. Considering the above, How, equipped with such political philosophy, the illiberals would undertake the subtle game with globalization? Could illiberal democracy ever be the answer?

We can consider several clues. She feels sympathy for the populist constituency, which she thinks is formed by a lower middle class, a mirror image of Poland's distorted capitalism, a class of small producers whose aspirations have been blocked by expensive credit, uneven competition with western markets, and monetary policy undercutting exports. She feels satisfaction that that hard-working class has been revindicated.¹¹⁰ She is dismissive of the alarms about the illiberal right's authoritarian tendencies, simply because her own thinking about the place of post-communism in the globalized world excludes the possibility of dictatorship.¹¹¹ So illiberal shake-up of the state could not be very harmful, even if it was not salutary. More importantly, in yearning for the resistance, she began to recognize rationality in the irrational, beginning with reappraising Solidarity's rebellion. Solidarity might have been irrational in evoking the cardinal values of the system it was opposing, but the collective agency built upon moral fundamentalism outlasted communism's erosion, and that weighted more. The irrational was thus an indispensable trigger of the modernization process, and thus on balance was "historically rational", despite creating turbulences after the take-off. In this

¹⁰⁹ Staniszkis, "Wstyd!" (2001), ZWNP, 631.

¹¹⁰ Staniszkis, "Demokracja w krzywym zwierciadle" (2001), ZWNP, 630.

¹¹¹ Staniszkis, *Postkomunizm*, 11.

way, JS' own journey away from neo-Marxism puts Hegel on its head. If it is true that rebellion can't transgress the system, when it is epistemologically rooted in that system, then all rational efforts to transgress modernity can only yield “artificial negativity”, a sort of contestation that ultimately makes modern rationality stronger. “Paradoxically, rebellion as an impulse for modernisation thus requires neo-traditionalization”.¹¹²

With the imperative to resist Poland's global drift in mind, JW would support the two consecutive bids for power of the Polish illiberals from PiS, in 2005 and in 2015, irritated with what she perceived as pro-Western short-sightedness of the politicians of the left-liberal camp, their complacent attitude towards the weakness of the state and its geopolitical drift. As if reenacting a pattern established with the AWS experience and even earlier with the acceleration camp, she would conclude again and again that while illiberals eagerly borrow from her critiques, their understanding of means and purposes of government is even more archaic and primitive. About the last iteration of the PiS government she would conclude in 2016 that Kaczyński was fighting post-communism with neo-bolshevism, with its rule through societal conflict, destruction of institutions and instrumental treatment of the law. At the end of the day, she hoped that overcoming post-communism would make Poland a normal Western country. She was frustrated to see how struggle against post-communism pushed Poland eastwards.¹¹³

Conclusion

Our central question about Jadwiga Staniszkis' relationship to illiberalism has no straightforward answer, regardless whether we put her ideas or her politics first. It is obvious which elements of her intellectual legacy were most eagerly weaponized by the illiberals: the critique of post-communism as powerless democracy and capitalism deformed by communist deep state with its tentacles connecting economy to secret services, and her censure of post-dissident liberalism as clueless Westernism of comprador elites. But the more you scratch under the surface, the more heterogenous the image of her ideological affinities. There is a neoliberal Staniszkis, with her criticism of the non-transformative character of Solidarity's rebellion, her lyrical image of capitalism, and her adoration of the sturdy individual, taken

¹¹² Staniszkis, “Ciągłość i Zmiana”, 159. Nota bene, there is an interesting parallelism with Paul Piccone's evolution, who in the 1990s abandoned the and looked to the Right for examples of organic negativity (such as Liga Nord and the French New Right) that could support his project of “federalist populism”. Paul Piccone, “From the New Left to the New Populism”, *Telos* 101 (1994): 173–208. doi:10.3817/0994101173

¹¹³ Grzegorz Osiecki, “Postkomunizm umarł, niech żyje postkomunizm”, *Dziennik.pl*, 11 June 2016. <https://wiadomosci.dziennik.pl/opinie/artykuly/523250.postkomunizm-umarl-niech-zyje-postkomunizm-kaczynski-stosuje-schematy-ktore-wymyslil-na-poczatku-lat-90.html>

from Camus, but bringing to mind Ayn Rand. But that coexists with a possible image of Staniszkis as an intellectual of the old left moved by a sense of obligation towards common people in their struggle “against bosses, against oligarchies,” imagining an Austrian-style corporatist political order as best for Poland, patriotic while critical of excesses of nationalism. For it must again be emphasized, that in many aspects of the culture wars illiberals were waging, Staniszkis was either neutral or defending liberal positions, as in the case of the *Neighbours* (that stellar example of the liberal “pedagogy of shame”), or Rospuda (the EU-ecologist conspiracy against Poland’s extractivist ambitions), or her embrace of the Lisbon Treaty (introducing the dictatorship of EU bureaucrats). Even though she appreciated the “organic negativity” of the traditionalist opposition to modernity, Staniszkis cautioned against theocratic tendencies in Polish public life, and in the later part of her career took inspiration from Taoism (an aspect of her thought we did not have space to cover!). Not to mention that what the Right embraced in Staniszkis as the conservative *neo-endecja* realism, in fact has its roots in neo-Marxist critical theory.

And that brings us to perhaps the most important point. For the same way of thinking that her admirers read as reminiscence of *endecja*, and what in fact has roots in neo-Marxism, her liberal opponents preferred to read as conspiracy theories, the signature trait of illiberal populism. And in the triangle of *neo-endecja* realism, neo-Marxism, and conspiracy theory, we have the kind of thinking that pays attention to powerful actors working behind the scenes to orchestrate events according with their often illicit interests and plans, making mockery of the representative institutions and the law. Indeed these have been some of the main themes of JS’ work, heavily conditioned by both her experience of March 1968 and the kind of social science world she grew into. But as scholars who work on conspiracy theories admit, lizard people and other glaringly surreal fantasies, distract our attention from the fact that conspiracy theories have an extensive grey area in which incessant boundary work is taking place.¹¹⁴ This is because *conspiracies* do happen, some of them do involve elites and state agents, and gaslighting critics (raising suspicions of their paranoia) often serves as a cover up. And this is also because social *theories* in general, and theories about power in particular, sometimes reason in terms of a two-tier reality, one accessible to the ordinary people, and other to the sociologist (the one in the know), and in the latter powerful forces are at play and they are powerful precisely because they operate behind the veil of ignorance. *Nota bene*, Staniszkis is

¹¹⁴ Michael Butter and Peter Knight, eds., *Routledge Handbook of Conspiracy Theories* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2020).

an interesting case in point that the boundary work of distinguishing legitimate critique from paranoia, works differently in politics and in science. While she earned the title of conspiracy theorist for her political commentary early in the 1990s, in 2004 for the science that supported the commentary she was awarded the Foundation for Polish Science Award, a.k.a. the Polish Nobel prize. So, does she deserve the one or the other? Some of her analyses seem in fact quite prescient, in particular the concept of “exclusive corporatism” is ripe for revisiting in this day and age of hyper-polarization. She wasn’t wrong about the excesses of neoliberalization of international order such as the MAI. Others, admittedly, do get her in the grey zone of conspiracist thinking. For example, her claim that the formation of the euro-regions would lead to partition of Poland was widely exaggerated, confusing unlikely consequences with intentional actions. Similarly, she does not provide any evidence of comparable strength to support her strong conviction that secret services actively manipulated the process of capitalist restructuring, securing the competitive advantage for nomenklatura while also blackmailing them – as if a power positions in the old regime were not enough to secure a head start. However, while the illiberal right has eagerly turned this element of her theory as the core justification of their assaults on post-communism, in fact it was actually never that central. Her central point was that geopolitical and material interests were the true drivers of the breakthrough of 1989, rather than the illusion of political agency of dissidents turned liberal politicians. And that central point was both well evidenced and open to contingency – Moscow and Warsaw communists were intending to save the system through radical measures that got out of hand. Again, if that is a conspiracy theory, than so is Stephen Kotkin’s work!

Perhaps most importantly, while JS’ way of theorising –foregrounding that power resides not where people believe it resides, and since they have a wrong concept power they are bad at exercising it– might imply holding post-dissident liberalism in contempt, it does not necessarily lead to embrace of illiberalism. A great example is Robert Krasowski, editor, publisher and writer, who not only counts among JS’ greatest admirers and has made her idea of power axis of his own narratives about politics after 1989. Now, that embrace of Staniszkis’ concept of power has led Krasowski towards a position of a cynical detachment. In his multi-volume history of post-communist Poland, he asserts that the transition was a process in which the direction was set by the West and whose impetus and ultimate success was the work of Polish society and its dynamism, whereas politicians were of secondary importance. To say that they were imitators is an “unearned flattery”. In fact he must have had

Staniszkis in mind, when he observed: “In the transition, politics had little impact, competence or merit. We don’t acknowledge that because of an intellectual mistake, which deforms our whole thinking about politics. We dramatically exaggerate the power of politics, in Poland in particular. Politicians are seen as directors of every important breakthrough...Logically, the success of the transition was taken as evidence of their greatness. Assaults on that greatness were read not as assaults on [concept of] politics, but as assaults on reality itself”.¹¹⁵ While that explains why Staniszkis was labelled a conspiracy theorist by the post-dissident liberals, perhaps the more pertinent question, which leads us towards the meanders of her own politics, is why Staniszkis is not more like Robert Krasowski? Why she chose a position of partisanship, rather than detachment? Why, instead taking scorning distance from the shallows of Polish politics in general, she found herself in the orbit of illiberalism?

I think this is because she remained true to her dissident understanding of the public role of intellectual in which loyalty and voice, risk and critique, come intertwined. You testify to seriousness of your beliefs by standing up for them. Fair critique is immanent critique. You can only criticize a given group when you take risks together. Now, it seems to be the case that illiberalism offered more space for Jadwiga Staniszkis to stay true to her dissident calling, while liberalism, despite its declarative commitment to pluralism, resulted to be much less patient with her critiques. Despite the fact that she was not milder in her judgements about illiberalism and its failures, and despite the fact she was at odds with many elements of the illiberal ideological package.

That perhaps can issue in some fresh insights about the nature of illiberalism’s allure. Illiberalism in Central Europe has had a triumphant phase, which however has been preceded by a militant phase.¹¹⁶ The triumphant phase might well be all about the supreme leader, ideological cohesion, and instrumentalizing law to consolidate power. But just as we should avoid the illusion of continuity in writing biographies, projecting these qualities backwards will yield a distorted picture of the militant phase. The strength of that phase derived from internal pluralism. During the militant phase, the illiberal camp adopted a big tent strategy, providing a platform which attracted a motley crew of critics of the transition, that included Staniszkis, but also the sociologist Piotr Gliški, expert on green social movements and civil

¹¹⁵ Robert Krasowski, *Po Południu: Upadek Elit Solidarnościowych po Zdobyciu Władzy* (Warszawa: Czerwone i Czarne, 2012), 339.

¹¹⁶ I borrow these terms from Gombrich who distinguished in the medieval history of art the phases of “militant Church” and a “triumphant Church”. E. H. Gombrich, *The Story of Art*, (London: Phaidon, 1992).

society, turned minister of culture in 2015-2023, or the philosopher Zdzisław Krasnodębski, an expert on postmodernity turned PiS MEP. Our understanding of contemporary illiberalism will be richer if we get a better grasp of the heterogeneity of intentions with which the road to its triumph was paved, the real intellectual multiplicity of its coalitions that definitely strengthened the illiberal project.

That this is more than a Polish specificity. In fact, Naomi Klein has learned that same lesson by following the life trajectory of her doppelganger, Naomi Wolf, a writer and activist Klein gets confused with a lot, who moved from icon of third wave feminism celebrated for the *Beauty Myth* (1990), to heroine of the COVID-19 denialist movement, and a frequent and dear guest of Steve Bannon's War Room podcast. In addition to offsetting the collateral damage to her own reputation, Klein considers Wolf's case insightful for the larger audience because she represents the vanguard of diagonalism.¹¹⁷ As Callison and Slobodian define it,¹¹⁸ diagonalism is the characteristic shared by many movements that rose in protest against COVID-19 countermeasures, namely, a postmodern, "out of the box" blend of beliefs coming from different ideological corners, from feminism and New Age holism to praise of gun ownership, all hold together by a libertarian sense of freedom and its correlative belief that all power is conspiracy (of deep state, big pharma, or big tech among others). Klein saw how the rise of diagonalism has elicited different reactions on the illiberal right, that embraced it, and the liberal Left, that dismissed it. The left turned out to be much more preoccupied with the integrity of beliefs and afraid of the "conspiracy theory" label, while the intellectually promiscuous Bannon, eagerly tolerated Wolf's feminism as a small price to be paid for reclaiming for the illiberal project the value of pluralism and the virtue of speaking truth to power, which the left once cherished, but ditched in favour of respectability. In other words, for the Left, the diagonalist is a doppelganger, one looks at with horror precisely because of all the things that feel uncannily familiar. Horror, in turn, leads to further atrophy of critical thinking and courage to debunk real conspiracies of the powerful against the weak, which has always been the calling of the progressives. Ultimately, then, diagonalism is revealing of an ideological field of forces, in which the illiberals thrive thanks to a big tent strategy, while the left is afraid of its own shadow. That constellation might be new for North America, but Jadwiga Staniszkis' own diagonalism shows, it is far from unprecedented in Central Europe.

¹¹⁷ Naomi Klein, *Doppelganger: A Trip into the Mirror World* (New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2023).

¹¹⁸ William Callison and Quinn Slobodian, "Coronapolitics from the Reichstag to the Capitol", *Boston Review*, 12 January 2021.